

Inka and non-Inka groups in Cusco, Peru

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This entry uses ethnohistoric and archaeological evidence to reconstruct religious practices and beliefs among Inka and non-Inka social groups in the late pre-contact Cusco region, the former Inka imperial heartland. The late pre-contact period began with political decentralization and competition between ethnic groups. Leading up to imperial expansion, the Inkas increasingly formalized institutions and developed novel religious practices related to agricultural cycles and mummified ancestors. Meanwhile, non-Inka groups in the surrounding region variably established alliances with the Inkas while likely maintaining relative autonomy and diverse religious practices related to local landscape features. Though Inka religion in Cusco has been extensively studied, understanding neighbouring groups' religious beliefs and practices is necessary to reconstruct the cultural context and sociopolitical dynamics implicated in Inka state formation.

Date Range: 900 CE - 1532 CE

Region: Cusco region (Inka imperial heartland)

Region tags: Cusco, Andes

This area provides a rough extension of the immediate interaction sphere that the Inkas engaged most intensively during the initial phases of state formation. This region also presents a high concentration of imperial infrastructure as well as royal estates and monuments that supported Inka sovereign ideology and political economy.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bauer, B. (1998). *The Sacred Landscape of the Inca: The Cusco ceque system*. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press.
- Source 2: Polo de Ondegardo, J. (2023[1566]). *Carta-relación del licenciado Polo Ondegardo al arzobispo Jerónimo de Loayza sobre creencias y prácticas mortuorias de los pueblos indígenas del Perú* (G. Lamana, Ed.). Ms. 0767, Rare Book and Manuscript Library, University of Illinois, Campus Urbana-Champaign. *Histórica XLVII(1):137-172*.
- Source 3: Molina, C. (2011[1573/1575]). *Account of the Fables and Rites of the Incas* (B. Bauer, V. Smith-Oka, and G. Cantarutti, Trans., Eds.). Austin, TX: University of Texas Press.

Notes: There are numerous texts that deal with Inka religion in general, but few focus on pre-contact religion specifically in Cusco. Bauer's book presents a comprehensive reconstruction of the ritual landscape surrounding the city of Cusco, based on archaeological and historical evidence. Polo de

Ondegardo's early colonial letter provides rare insight into Inka and non-Inka populations' beliefs and practices, based on his travels through Cusco and Charcas (modern-day Bolivia). Lastly, early colonial writer Molina offers additional information on elite and non-elite beliefs and rituals in Cusco and its environs. Combined, these three texts constitute a good starting point for understanding this topic, albeit significant gaps in knowledge remain, specifically regarding the practices and beliefs of non-elites.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The late pre-contact Andes was a highly diverse, decentralized religious landscape. Each locality had its own local wak'as (non-human) and apus (agentive mountains) that were foci of local religion and ritual. Based on the accounts of colonial-era "extirpators of idolatry," religious practices were highly personalized in many cases, and individuals readily identified and kept objects of worship (wak'as) without requiring approval from an institutionalized religious authority. Nevertheless, religions were more institutionalized and hierarchical in the case of the Inka and Chimu states that sought to co-opt religious ideology as a power strategy. In sum, numerous religions coexisted during this period and were in contact with one another.

Reference: de Arriaga, Pablo Jose. *La Extirpación De La Idolatría En El Perú*. Cusco, Peru: Centro de Estudios Regionales Andinos "Bartolomé de Las Casas", 1999.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Reference: Bauer, Brian S., and R. Alan Covey. "Processes of State Formation in the Inca Heartland (cuzco, Peru)" 104, no. 3 (September 2002). <https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.2002.104.3.846>.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Violent conflict within Cusco is still an ongoing topic of debate. Ethnohistoric accounts describe a period of chronic warfare preceding Inka state formation. However, these accounts are seen as possibly ideological in nature, serving to justify Inka governance as having a

pacifying effect on Andean societies. While archaeological evidence of warfare remains elusive, local sites in regions such as the Sacred Valley and Lucre Basin present perimeter walls and fortifications. Weapons such as stone clubs and fragments of burnt architectural daub further suggest ongoing hostilities. However, further research is needed to determine the extent and severity of intergroup conflict during this period.

Reference: Bauer, Brian S.. *Ancient Cuzco: Heartland of the Inca*. Austin, TX: University of Texas at Austin, 2004.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Reference: Arkush, Elizabeth, Weston C. McCool, and Ryan D. Smith. "The Late Intermediate Period in the South-central Andes (AD 1000–1450): Key Problems in Chronology", October 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2023.10.002>.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: This is true in the case of aqllakuna (female religious specialists), who are selected for this role in childhood (see above).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– I don't know

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Locality and region (i.e., one must worship the local deities of the locality where they are from)

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The religion of Inka elites in Cusco became the state religion. Inka political authority was legitimized by their religious ideology, such that Inka political organization is sometimes described as a theocracy. As for local non-elite religions, these were likely integrated with local political structures. Isbell's influential book "Mummies and Mortuary Monuments" alleged that local political hierarchies were closely tied to ancestor veneration. However, the relationship between local religions and political structure remains to be more thoroughly evaluated.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Inka religious specialists, nameley priests and aqllakuna ("chosen women"), were supported by the state. As for non-elite populations, it is unlikely that they had full-time religious specialists that were supported by the community.

Reference: Covey, Alan R.. *Inca Apocalypse: The Spanish Conquest and the Transformation of the Andean World*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 2020.

Reference: D'Altroy, Terence N.. *The Incas*. 2nd ed.. Wiley Blackwell, 2014.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Notes: Subject populations were obliged to pay tribute to the Inka state religion and recognize the Inka ruler's religious authority, but were not obliged to abandon their own local religions to observe the state religion. However, the Inkas sometimes destroyed or "kidnapped" local wak'as and objects of worship as a means of punishment or subjugation.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: No incidents of apostasy have been recorded, to my knowledge.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 150000

Notes: It is very difficult to estimate population size, given that we have no preserved record. The population size would have also varied significantly over the course of this period, growing by the 15th century with the settling of mitmaqkuna (colonists) and yanakuna (retainers) in and around the capital. However, site sizes are relatively small and dispersed in the Cusco region, compared with other areas. Scholars have estimated that the city of Cusco had a population of up to 20,000, and in all its hinterland there were as many as 150,000 people.

Reference: D'Altroy, Terence N.. *The Incas*. 2nd ed.. Wiley Blackwell, 2014.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative

and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: Writing did not exist in pre-contact Cusco. Religious ideas would have been conveyed through oral histories, rituals, song, dance, and material culture.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Carved rock outcrops

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Little is known of the religious iconography of this region. For example, what preserves of Inka and local material culture is largely limited to pottery. We do not know much about how religious and public spaces were decorated, nor about how individuals decorated their bodies. Geometric motifs are recurrent in pottery, textiles, and architecture. There are accounts that the faces of elite persons were painted with human or camelid blood during important Inka ceremonies. So-called face-neck jars that were produced both Inka and non-Inka populations in the Cusco region also present distinctive face paint designs on anthropomorphic faces, which may have been tied to religious ceremonies. Some pottery such as Lucre style incorporate distinctive symbols that may have held religious meaning. However, little information is currently available to reconstruct Inka or local repertoires of religious iconography.

Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimages have long been an important religious practice for Andeans. Pilgrimages continue to hold great significance for people in the Cusco region, such as the famous Quyllurit'i, but have been Christianized. More generally, recurring journeys to locations such as mountain tops that are evocative and difficult to reach remain important practices within local communities, who often bring offerings for mountains and other non-human agents embodied in natural features. The Inkas elaborated on local religious practices by staging rituals involving animal and human sacrifices (qhapaq hucha), and by building distinctive shrines and facilities.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: Mass human sacrifices have been identified near elite cemetery areas at Saqsaywaman, but these sacrifices are not interred together in the same graves as elite individuals. See M. Paredes (2003) "PRÁCTICAS FUNERARIAS INCAICAS EN SACSAYHUAMÁN: ENTERRAMIENTOS CEREMONIALES Y COMPLEJO FUNERARIO".

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Yes

Notes: In the human sacrifice burials at Muyuqmarka (Saqsaywaman), no analyses have been yet carried out to determine the geographic or ethnic origin of the individuals. However, comparisons with other accounts of human sacrifice may offer clues. For example, in qhapaq hucha ceremonies carried out on mountain tops, children from distant territories across the empire were recruited as sacrificial victims. It is likely that

human sacrifices within the capital of Cusco also involved individuals from provinces. Overall, based on written accounts, it does not appear that the Inkas sacrificed members of the elite ruling class in Cusco. Therefore, while further research is necessary, it is safe to say that the Inkas sacrificed "out-group humans" for burial ceremonies of elite individuals.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Llamas were primarily sacrificed at important ceremonies.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Reference: Flammang, Amandine. "Inca Funerary Practices (ca. 1400–1532): A First Assessment on the Basis of Archaeological Data" 42, no. 2 (November 21, 2021).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2021.1986274>.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Mortuary contexts have documented personal affects including tools such as weaving implements that are surmised to have been used by the interred individual during his/her lifetime.

Reference: Flammang, Amandine. "Inca Funerary Practices (ca. 1400–1532): A First Assessment on the Basis of Archaeological Data" 42, no. 2 (November 21, 2021).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2021.1986274>.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Burials have been so heavily looted in Cusco that most wealth items associated with burials are gone. The most high-status wealth items would have been associated

with Inka royalty, who were not buried so to speak, but remained active members of society and participated in social events.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Burials have been excavated or identified with fine Inka pottery, for example at Machu Picchu and Saqsaywaman.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– I don't know

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Cliffside tombs including capsules (individual) and mausolea (collective)

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Colonial documents also mention a creator god named Viracocha who takes an anthropomorphic form. Given that Andean peoples have often recognized the sacred in aniconic, natural forms, such as distinctively shaped rock formations or agricultural products, it is unclear to what extent the idea of an anthropomorphic god is truly pre-contact or reflects an early Christian influence. It could also be that anthropomorphic gods were popularized by state governments such as the Inkas to naturalize authority.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Inkas developed a sun cult, deeming the sun (Inti) to be the supreme god. It is unknown to what extent local non-state populations held an idea of a supreme or creator god previously.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Notes: I'm not sure, since the supreme god is the sun, it is likely that the sun could only see when visible in the sky, such that it may not have been able to see at night. It's difficult to say!

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - No
 - Notes: It depends on how much each chronicler tries to liken Inti to the Christian god, but I think that emotion was generally not attributed to the sun.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human

affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No

- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: The appearance of certain kinds of animals (e.g., hummingbird)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Wak'as and apus were not necessarily omniscient, but there is no reason to think that their knowledge was inherently restricted, either. See Tamara Bray's edited volume "Archaeology of Wak'as", 2015. In modern communities, wak'as may inflict negative consequences as punishment on people and families for wrongdoing, suggesting that they have knowledge of private matters.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: In many Andean oral histories, it seems that the line between human and "divine" or "supernatural" figure is fairly blurry. The Huarochiri Manuscript provides several good examples of how this is conceptualized. One example describes a human (Chaupi Ñamca) turning into a supernatural being (wak'a) after initiating a sexual relationship with a supernatural being. Though this text pertains to the area near Lima (central Peru), a similar situation could be modelled for Cusco. Oral histories told by some local community members in Cusco today describe humans doing supernatural or "magical" acts, such as changing the form of the landscape, but these details emerge as the story continues. In other words, these individuals are not explicitly introduced as "divine" or "supernatural" beings. The Inkas described their mythical ancestors in a way that made their "semi-divine" status more explicit. Their origin is said to be either from a lake or a cave (depending on the version of the story); these mythical ancestors are described as performing superhuman acts, including the transformation of landscape features, or having wings and flying. However, they are mortal, and eventually die.

Reference: Salomon, Frank, and G. Urioste, eds.. *The Huarochiri Manuscript: A Testament of Ancient and Colonial Andean Religion*. Edited by Frank Salomon and G. Urioste. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 1991.

Reference: Sarmiento de Gamboa, Pedro. *The History of the Incas*. Edited by Brian S. Bauer and Vania Smith. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2007.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– I don't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: To some extent this may be true, although there is reason to believe where hierarchies existed, they were flexible and subject to change. Compare, for example, the Huarochiri Manuscript's description of local wak'as and the social relationships between them, which has been compared to mythological narratives associated with pantheons in other contexts, such as the Greco-Roman world.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Generally gods (wak'as) are highly local, somewhat like European saint cults and shrines. This changes with states such as the Inkas, where religion is mobilized as a power strategy, and a sun god is established who receives offerings and worship from across the empire. A similar situation for local and state gods can be proposed for other Andean states, such as the Wari, Tiwanku, and Chimu.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: An example might be bad dreams or a feeling of dread.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: This is probably one of the most common punishments mentioned

ethnographically by modern communities.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– I don't know

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– I don't know

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of individuals and concepts that could be considered broadly similar to the idea of a messiah, although not precisely equivalent to the Jewish concept. As mentioned above in the case of anthropomorphic deities, it is unclear to what extent these semblances resulted from Christianization. Taking the idea of a messiah as an individual who initiates a fundamental transformation of the world, this definition could describe the Inka ruler Yupanki, who later took the name "Pachakuti", literally meaning "the one who transforms the world". However, this is not an identity that was necessarily foretold. During the early colonial period, Indigenous Andeans developed a belief in the Inkari associated with the taki onqoy religious movement that foretold of the return of the Inka ruler Atawallpa and the restoration of Indigenous sovereignty.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: As for the Inkari prophecy, it is believed that Atawallpa's head is located in Cusco and his feet are in Ayacucho, such that he will reemerge from these places.

↳ Alive, identified:

– No

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

- ↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Coming has already passed:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:
 - No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
– Yes

↳ Other purpose:
– I don't know

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Indigenous Andeans appear to have conceptualized time and space as cyclical, such that there does not appear to be a documented sense that this cycle will end in Andean belief systems.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Social norms prescribed by religion appear more related to mortuary practice. That is, respect and care for the dead through varying practices were the "norm". It is popularly stated that the Inkas promoted social norms through a moral code that roughly translates to "do not lie, do not steal, do not be lazy". However, the extent to which such a code was really used in pre-contact times or is more of a colonial invention is unclear. Moreover, it does not appear to be related to religion.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: There are claims that members of religious groups such as aqllas (who were conceptualized in colonial times as nuns) were virgins and priests had to undertake periods of abstinence. However, many of these accounts appear to be influenced by Christian norms. There are also claims that some male priests were homosexual or dressed as women (Zuidema). Overall, it is difficult to reconstruct sexual practices within Inka and pre-contact religions because of the biases of colonial sources (Covey, 2023).

Reference: Zuidema, Tom. *Inca Civilization in Cusco*. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 1990.

Reference: Covey, R. Alan. "Inca Religious Women in the Male Imagination" 103, no. 3 (March 27, 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1215/00182168-10588995>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See response above.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: There were periodic restrictions for certain rituals where ají (spicy peppers) and salt could not be consumed.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Consumption of chicha (corn beer) was a central practice of religious ceremonies.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

– A chiefdom

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Notes: Local societies were largely self-sufficient and managed storage of staple food items to protect against food insecurity. They also practiced diversification of subsistence practices, although this was limited when the Inkas demanded tribute in the form of labor and maize production. I have not come across any indication that any kind of famine relief was institutionalized.

Reference: D'Altroy, Terence N., Timothy K. Earle, David L. Browman, Darrell La Lone, Michael E. Moseley, John V. Murra, Thomas P. Myers, Frank Salomon, Katharina J. Schreiber, and John R. Topic. "Staple Finance, Wealth Finance, and Storage in the Inka Political Economy [and Comments and Reply]" 26, no. 2 (April 1985). <https://doi.org/10.1086/203249>.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: If any relief was provided, it would have been through state institutions or local leadership.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See responses above.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Mestizo chronicler Garcilaso de la Vega claimed that there were schools and universities in Cusco. However, this has not been verified. Another possible case is that the Inkas created the aqllawasi ("house of the chosen ones"), which is typically conceptualized as a religious institution like a cloister. The aqllawasis recruited young girls and taught them skills such as weaving and brewing, and also made them ritual specialists.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The legal code pertains to the Inka state rather than any religious group.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Inka state government provides the legal code. Aspects of this code can be surmised by chroniclers' descriptions of different punishments that were given for different crimes. However, much of this information can be subject to scrutiny. In some cases, chroniclers or their informants may have exaggerated the harshness of penalties or manipulated what acts were considered criminal. They may have done this intentionally to promote an idea that Inka and Spanish society were alike, and that the Inkas could be considered "civilized." For example, Indigenous chronicler Guaman Poma de Ayala

claimed the Inkas inflicted extremely harsh penalties for unsanctioned sexual acts. Conversely, other colonial writers that lacked this motive describe Andean attitudes toward intercourse perhaps more realistically, as Arriaga complained that Indigenous Andeans did not share the Christian idea that individuals should remain virgins until marriage. This is just one example, but it illustrates some of the difficulties with interpreting chroniclers' claims about an Inka legal code and how illegal acts were punished.

Reference: Guaman Poma de Ayala, Felipe. *Nueva Corónica Y Buen Gobierno* (codex Péruvien Illustré). Paris: Institut d'ethnologie, 1936. <https://bvpb.mcu.es/iberoamerica/es/consulta/registro.do?control=BVPBB20170009771>.

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Reference: de Arriaga, Pablo Jose. *La Extirpación De La Idolatría En El Perú*. Cusco, Peru: Centro de Estudios Regionales Andinos "Bartolomé de Las Casas", 1999.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Written language is not known to have existed among pre-contact highland Andean peoples. However, a record keeping device called a khipu was used largely for administrative purposes by state officials.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Patorialism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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